

Original Article

Role of *Cassia angustifolia* in the Treatment of COVID-19 – In Silico Activity of Emodin against SARS-CoV-2 Spike Protein

Shaista Aslam¹, Rana Khurram Aftab², Ahmad Tariq², Avais Ahmad³, Musarrat Ijaz⁴, Noor e Hira⁵

¹National University of Medical Sciences, Rawalpindi, Pakistan

²Punjab Institute of Cardiology, Lahore, Pakistan

³Continental Medical College, Lahore, Pakistan

⁴Islamia University Bahawalpur, Pakistan

⁵University of the Punjab, Lahore, Pakistan

*Corresponding Author: Shaista Aslam, PhD, Assistant Professor, Department of Biological Sciences, National University of Medical Sciences Rawalpindi (Pakistan). Email: shaista.aslam@numspak.edu.pk

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ABSTRACT

Background: Coronavirus epidemic has affected wide pulverization throughout the world. There is a plenty of data and falsehood via online media with respect to medications and treatment for it. One of the viral advice now a days is the use of *Cassia angustifolia* (Senna Makki). **Methodology:** This was an in-silico study to evaluate the efficacy of phytoconstituents of Senna against viral spike protein. **Results:** After docking several phytoconstituents of Senna using AutoDock 4, Emodin was found to best bind with the viral spike protein. **Conclusion:** Emodin shows great binding capacity with the SARS-CoronaV-2 spike protein and it has feasible pharmacokinetic properties to be used as a drug. Thus, we can infer that Emodin might be helpful for the management of COVID-19. Additional studies and trials are required to assess their actions.

Keywords: COVID-19, *Cassia angustifolia*, Senna Makki, In silico

Introduction

COVID-19 has been now spread in 234 nations with 211,582,355 affirmed cases and 4,428,230 expiries around the world. In Pakistan, there are 1.12 Million affirmed cases and 24,848 deaths.¹ This is an illness which regularly exhibit as tickle in throat,

pyrexia, and abnormal pneumonia and is caused by RNA virus; SARS-2-Coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2).² There is not any supported healing medication for it yet aside from Remdesivir which is famous to be powerful in beginning phase of the illness.³

For instance, the epidemic wins, there is a plenty of data and deception via online broadcasting with

respect to the beginning, commonness, and drug of the disease.⁴ One the greatest popular counsel in regard to the handling of COVID-19 dispersion these days on web is the utilization of a natural medication Senna Makki. There are a few cases on web with respect to its adequacy to really look at the infection. In any case, it is doubtful and involves conversation among doctors.⁵ Some specialists guarantee that because of its purgative nature, it very well may be hurtful and additionally deteriorate the disease.⁶

Senna Makki (*Cassia angustifolia*) is a dry season safe spice, local of Saudi Arabia and is presently become around the world. It is utilized as an anti-pyretic in splenic augmentations, iron deficiency, cholera, typhoid, and as a poison remover. It is likewise utilized in the handling of stoppage, ameboid looseness of the bowels, as an anthelmintic and as a gentle energizer. The imbue of plant is utilized in treating bronchitis, loose bowels, fever, hemorrhoids, diarrhea, and fevers.⁷

Studies have been done to discover the substance organization of Senna, different substances in it are Sitosterol, Sennosides A,B,C, anthraquinone, Cathartic corrosive, Rhamnetin, gluco-sennin, , chrysophenic corrosive, nigrin, kaemphrin, rhein, flavonoids, emodin and salicylic acid.^{7,8,9} Established on its compound arrangement, a few restorative impacts (like laxative, anti-infection, hostile to malarial, against malignant growth, antipyretic, cell reinforcement, calming and so forth) of Senna are depicted and considered.⁹

The occurrence of the mixtures; Emodin, Salicylic corrosive and anthraquinone are a state of fascination for us. Emodin has been distinguished as a composite with possible antiviral movement against these viruses.¹⁰ Inflammation¹¹, venous and blood vessel thromboembolic complications¹² are related with COVID-19. That is the reason calming drugs are additionally endorsed in its management.¹³ The mixtures in Senna may help mitigating just as hostile to oxidant capacities for

example Salicylic corrosive (acetyl salicylic corrosive is usually known as anti-inflammatory medicine) serves the mitigating just as against coagulant work in this manner might diminish the odds of advancement of Disseminated Intravascular Coagulation (DIC). Anthraquinone aids the cell reinforcement work hence may assist with relieving the oxidative pressure that is delivered in Corona-19.⁹

The existence of such mixtures in Senna recommends its possible job as a medication in the cure of this virus. Such therapeutic spices are utilized as corresponding or elective medications global ever since long.¹⁴ WHO convinces the investigation of viability and symptoms of restorative spices in view of leaning of individuals towards them and possible results of numerous engineered medicines.¹⁵ Motivated by these things; our point is to assess the in-silico action of Phyto-constituents of Senna Makki particularly emodin against the viral spike protein.

Methodology

Molecular docking is used to discover drugs by virtually docking molecules with the target macromolecules such as proteins and receptors. Docking generates various conformations based on the interactions of the molecules and calculate the binding energies and the most suitable results are sorted out¹⁶.

The three-D crystal structure of COVID-19 spike protein (PDB ID 6LU7) were recovered from the RCSB Protein Data Bank. The biochemical arrangement of the ligands was achieved from PubChem database compound. Various ligands were docked with the given receptors using AutoGrid and AutoDock 4 (The Scripps Research Institute) to find out the best suiting inhibitors.

The absorption, spreading, breakdown and elimination properties were designed by the use of smile notation in Swiss ADME web-based tool.¹⁷ The Bioavailability Score was designed by means of Mol-inspiration web-based tool.

Results

After docking several phytoconstituents of Senna, Emodin was found to best bind with the viral spike

protein. Using the SWISS-ADME tools the molecular properties and drug likeliness Emodin was found. Table 1 gives the pharmacokinetic properties of the drug Emodin.

Table 1: Pharmacokinetic Properties of Emodin

Feature	Emodin
1. Physicochemical Properties	
Molecular Formula	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₅
Molecular weight	270.24 g/mol
Num. heavy atoms	20
Num. aromatic heavy atoms	12
Num. rotatable bonds	0
Num. H-bond acceptors	5
Num. H-bond donors	3
Molar Refractivity	70.78
Topological Polar Surface Area (TPSA)	94.83 Å ²
2. Lipophilicity	
Log Po/w (iLOGP)	1.80
Log Po/w (XLOGP3)	2.72
Log Po/w (WLOGP)	1.89
Log Po/w (MLOGP)	0.36
Consensus Log Po/w	1.87
3. Water Solubility	
Log S (ESOL)	-3.67
Solubility	5.74e-02 mg/ml 2.12e-04 mol/l
Class	Soluble
4. Pharmacokinetics	
GI absorption	High
BBB permeant	No
P-glycoprotein substrate	No
CYP1A2 inhibitor	Yes
CYP2C19 inhibitor	No
CYP2C9 inhibitor	No
CYP2D6 inhibitor	No
CYP3A4 inhibitor	Yes
Log Kp (skin permeation)	-6.02 cm/s
5. Drug Likeness	
Lipinski	Yes
Ghose	Yes
Veber	Yes
Egan	Yes
Muegge	Yes

Bioavailability Score	0.55
6. Bioavailability Scores	
GPCR ligand	-0.14
Ion channel modulator	-0.14
Kinase inhibitor	0.07
Nuclear receptor ligand	0.17
Protease inhibitor	-0.21
Enzyme inhibitor	0.21

The docking score of Emodin shows good binding affinity with the viral spike protein along with the Inhibitory Potential expressed as kI and the Ligand Interactions. The docking score of Emodin with the viral spike protein is shown in the table 2.

Table 2: Docking Score, Inhibitory Potential and Interactions of Emodin

Compound	Binding Energy kCal/mol (kI) with GRB2	Ligand Interactions
Emodin	-8.54 (548.13nM)	3 Hydrogen, 1 alkyl, 2 pi-alkyl, 1 pi-pi T shaped bonds

Figure 1 illustrates the interactions of Emodin with the SARS-CoV-2 spike protein.

Fig 1. Interactions of Emodin with SARS-CoV-2 Spike Protein

Above indicated interactions of Emodin show its potential to be used as an inhibitor of SARS-CoV-2 spike protein in the treatment of COVID-19.

Discussion

With the approach of genomics, proteomics, bioinformatics and advancements like crystallography, NMR, the constructions of increasingly more protein targets are opening up. Thus, there is a requirement for computational instruments that can recognize and break down dynamic destinations and recommend potential medication particle that can tie to these locales. Docking is the computational assurance of restricting partiality between particles (protein construction and ligand). Given a protein and a ligand we could discover the limiting free energy of the complex shaped by docking them.

Essential sub-nuclear descriptors like sub-nuclear weight (MW), sub-nuclear refractive (MR), number of express molecule categories and polar surface district (PSA) are portrayed here. These properties are procured from the SwissADME electronic mechanical assembly. From the table 1 unquestionably Emodin is having 5 H-bond acceptors, 3 H-bond givers and there are 0 rotatable bond. The parcel coefficient amongst n-octanol and water ($\log P_{o/w}$) is the traditionally described for lipophilicity. SwissADME was utilized to anticipate the lipophilic person of the medication. SwissADME offers admittance to five openly accessible prescient models; for example XLOGP3, an atomistic strategy comprising remedial elements and information based library; WLOGP, their own execution of an absolutely atomistic technique dependent on the fragmental arrangement of Wildman and Crippen; MLOGP, a prime example of topological strategy depending on a straight connection with 13 sub-atomic descriptors; SILICOS-IT, a crossover strategy depending on twenty-seven sections and seven topological descriptors. Lastly iLOGP, our internal material science put together technique depending with respect to open energies of solvation in n-octanol and water determined by the Generalized-Born and

dissolvable open surface region (GB/SA) model. iLOGP was gauge on two medication or medication like outside sets. The distinctive lipophilicity of Emodin is displayed in the Table.1. Having a solvent atom enormously works with many medication advancement exercises, fundamentally the simplicity of taking care of and detailing. Besides, for revelation projects focusing on oral organization, dissolvability is one significant property impacting ingestion. Too, a medication implied for use should be profoundly dissolvable in water to convey a satisfactory amount of dynamic fixing in the little capacity of such drug measurement. There are two topological techniques to anticipate Water Solubility which are remembered for Swiss ADME. From Table 1 unmistakably Emodin is dissolvable in all perspectives.

The data of composites being substrate or non-substrate of the vulnerability glycoprotein (P-gp, proposed the main part among ATP-restricting tape carriers or ABC-carriers) is vital to assess dynamic discharge through organic films, for example from the digestive divider to the lumen or from the cerebrum. SwissADME empowers the assessment for a compound to be substrate of P-gp or inhibitor of the main CYP isoenzymes. The pharmacokinetic properties of Emodin were displayed in the table.1. Along these lines, from that obviously it's anything but a P-gp substrate.

Swiss ADME area offers admittance to five distinctive guideline-based channels, with assorted scopes of properties within which the atom is characterized as medication like. The Lipinski (Pfizer) channel is the forerunner rule-of-five, Ghose (Amgen), Veber (GSK), Egan (Pharmacia) and Muegge (Bayer) strategies are the five distinct principles. Any infringement of any standard portrayed here shows up unequivocally in the yield board. Quercetin is having bioavailability score of 0.55 and it shows no infringement in any of the angles in Ghose, Muegge techniques, Lipinski rule of five, Veber and Egan strategies.

Docking of little particle mixtures into the restricting area of a receptor and surveying the restricting favoritism of the complex is a huge piece of the development-based prescription design measure. AutoDock 4 is an open program designed for drug divulgence, nuclear docking and virtual screening, offering multicore limit, world class and further developed precision and comfort. The limits picked for the cropping can be chosen by the docking gadget's capacity to copy the restricting technique for a ligand to protein when the development of the ligand–protein intricate is recognized.

From the above given table 2, plainly Emodin has extraordinary docking ability with the viral spike protein and in this manner, there is an incredible capability of it being utilized as a medication against COVID-19. Emodin makes numerous Hydrogen bonds with the viral spike and can hinder its activity. Its belongings in the creature models and people should be tested.

Conclusion

Computational devices might be useful in discovering the reason for this disorder. PCOS is turning out to be more far reaching in the present situation and their variety is expanding at high speed along these lines a compelling and effective treatment is a critical need of present occasions. The review shows that Emodin has extraordinary restricting limit with the SARS-CoV-2 spike protein. In this manner, we can gather that it very well may be useful for the handling of COVID-19. Additional investigations and preliminaries are required to survey their activities.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of Interest.

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References

1. Fahmi I. World Health Organization coronavirus disease 2019 (Covid-19) situation report. DroneEmprit. 2019.
2. Cascella M, Rajnik M, Aleem A, Dulebohn S, Di Napoli R. Features, evaluation, and treatment of coronavirus (COVID-19). StatPearls. 2021 Apr 20.
3. Grein J, Ohmagari N, Shin D, Diaz G, Asperges E, Castagna A, Feldt T, Green G, Green ML, Lescure FX, Nicastri E. Compassionate use of remdesivir for patients with severe Covid-19. *New England Journal of Medicine*. 2020 Jun 11;382(24):2327-36.
4. Pennycook G, McPhetres J, Zhang Y, Lu JG, Rand DG. Fighting COVID-19 misinformation on social media: Experimental evidence for a scalable accuracy-nudge intervention. *Psychological science*. 2020 Jul;31(7):770-80.
5. <https://www.technologytimes.pk/2020/06/07/sanna-makki-a-herb-treatment-for-covid-19/>
6. <https://www.geo.tv/latest/292182-fact-check-sanna-makki-not-a-cure-for-coronavirus-can-cause-harm-if-overdosed>
7. Deshpande HA, Bhalsing SR. Recent advances in the phytochemistry of some medicinally important Cassia species: A review. *International journal of pharma medicine and biological sciences*. 2013;2(3):60-78.
8. Murti PB, Seshadri TR. Chemical composition of Indian senna leaves (*Cassia angustifolia*). In *Proceedings of the Indian Academy of Sciences-Section A* 1939 Aug (Vol. 10, No. 2, pp. 96-103). Springer India.
9. Tripathi YC. *Cassia angustifolia*, a versatile medicinal crop. *International Tree Crops Journal*. 1999 Jan 1;10(2):121-9.
10. Ho TY, Wu SL, Chen JC, Li CC, Hsiang CY. Emodin blocks the SARS coronavirus spike protein and angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 interaction. *Antiviral research*. 2007 May 1;74(2):92-101. doi:10.1016/j.antiviral.2006.04.014
11. Tay MZ, Poh CM, Rénia L, MacAry PA, Ng LF. The trinity of COVID-19: immunity, inflammation and intervention. *Nature Reviews Immunology*. 2020 Jun;20(6):363-74.
12. Lodigiani C, Iapichino G, Carenzo L, Cecconi M, Ferrazzi P, Sebastian T, Kucher N, Studt JD,

- Sacco C, Alexia B, Sandri MT. Venous and arterial thromboembolic complications in COVID-19 patients admitted to an academic hospital in Milan, Italy. *Thrombosis research*. 2020 Jul 1;191:9-14.
13. Stebbing J, Phelan A, Griffin I, Tucker C, Oechsle O, Smith D, Richardson P. COVID-19: combining antiviral and anti-inflammatory treatments. *The Lancet Infectious Diseases*. 2020 Apr 1;20(4):400-2.
 14. Mirhoseini M, Baradaran A, Rafieian-Kopaei M. Medicinal plants, diabetes mellitus and urgent needs. *Journal of HerbMed Pharmacology*. 2013;2(2).
 15. WHO Traditional Medicine Strategy 2014-23. China: WHO; 2013
 16. Wadood A, Ahmed N, Shah L, Ahmad A, Hassan H, Shams S. In-silico drug design: An approach which revolutionarised the drug discovery process. *OA drug design & delivery*. 2013 Sep 1;1(1):3.
 17. Daina A, Michielin O, Zoete V. SwissADME: a free web tool to evaluate pharmacokinetics, drug-likeness and medicinal chemistry friendliness of small molecules. *Scientific reports*. 2017 Mar 3;7(1):1-3.

Contributions of the Authors

SA, RKA devised the plan

AT,AA wrote the manuscript

MI,NEH did overall supervision

AT,MI, NEH repharsed and did statistical anayses

